

THEORETICAL OF THE DIAMETER OF THE ROLLER MILL OF THE MACHINE, WHICH PROCESSES THE PLOWED LANDS BY TRACE

Toirov Ravshanbek

Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology

Annotation: expressions are presented on the theoretical basis of the diameter of the reel of the machine, which processes the plowed lands in a trace.

Keywords: plow, rake, mola, rectifier, physical, mechanical, radius, diameter, construction.

In our Republic, at present, the preparation of newly evicted lands for planting has been carried out many times separately with gear and disc struts and various mola-rectifiers. From this, most farmers prepare the wheat and wheat-depleted fields planted in the open field for repeated crops by plowing them, burying plant residues, and then chizelling, pressing the plows and moles, or first molting and then working with the plows. In this, ground handling machines and weapons are used, which are mainly used in cotton growing, that is, driving the ground ld-100,

PLN-4-35, PYA-3-35, with PD-4-45 plugs, ground surface layer softening chku-4A, CHK-3.0 scratches, BDT-3.0, BDT-2.2 disc studs, Б3TX-1,0; Б3TC-1,0;

Bztx-1,0; BZTS-1,0; bzss-1,0 gear gears, while ground leveling and compaction are VP-8, MV-6 and MV-6,5 rectifiers and

mola-is carried out using rectifiers. But this is the soil of

deterioration of physical and mechanical properties leads to a large loss of moisture from the soil and an increase in fuel consumption and other costs. An analysis of scientific achievements on a global scale and previously performed research in our republic shows that these shortcomings in the preparation of new plowed lands for planting can be eliminated by developing a machine that adds all technological processes for preparing the soil for planting in one transition from the field (full

compaction of the plowed field, leveling and grinding the surface. The application of such a machine in pre-planting processing on newly plowed lands to increase the productivity of the enterprise, along with a sharp reduction in the number of transitions from the field to the aggregates, fuel consumption and other costs due to the addition of various technological processes,

it allows you to improve the quality of soil processing and prevent the loss of moisture in it, plant crops in a timely manner and collect minced meat. From these assertions, a combinatorial machine was developed that was used in the processing of new plowed lands at QXMITI [1; 2]. This machine is made up of disc coils and rectifier and plankali coils mounted in series on the common frame, loosening the soil in one pass through the field, leveling its surface, and grinding and compacting and preparing it for planting. But the parameters of the working bodies of this machine, including the planked reel, are not scientifically substantiated.

In this article, a machine that processes track-by-track on plowed lands is a theoretical justification of these specified parameters of a threaded Planck reel. Akhmedov, S. Aminov, A. To khtaqaziev, I. Inayatov, O'. Studies by Boboev .

From the condition that the diameter of the Helix runs through the incisions found in the Helix path, we define by the following expression

$$D \geq \frac{d_k [1 + \cos(\varphi_1 + \varphi_2)] + 2h_0}{1 - \cos(\varphi_1 + \varphi_2)} \quad (1)$$

or

$$R \geq \frac{d_k [1 + \cos(\varphi_1 + \varphi_2)] + h_0}{1 - \cos(\varphi_1 + \varphi_2)}, \quad (1, a)$$

where D is the diameter of the reel, m;

r_k , d_k -of incisions occurring in the path of the reel, respectively

radius and diameter, m;

φ_1 , φ_2 are the outer (i.e. to the metal) and inner (i.e. to the metal) of the incisions, respectively

soil) friction angles, degrees.

(1) and (1, a) if the conditions are met, the spool will climb over the incisions found in the road and crush them, otherwise there will be a heap of the incisions in front of the spool, and as a result, the specified technological process will not be performed. [5]

We define the diameter of the Helix bases by the following expression

$$D_a = D - 2(h_n - h_a) \quad (2)$$

or (3.29) considering the expression, or (3.29) considering the expression

$$D_a \geq \frac{d_k [1 + \cos(\varphi_1 + \varphi_2)] + 2h_0}{1 - \cos(\varphi_1 + \varphi_2)} - 2(h_n - h_a). \quad (2, a)$$

We take 0.6 cm and 25 cm, respectively, based on previous studies, literature and existing designs of sprockets with a threaded bar, both the thickness of the bases of the sprockets and the distance between them.

So, calculations according to the expressions obtained show that the diameter of the drum of a machine performing high-quality processing at the required level with low energy consumption on plowed land should be at least 36 cm, and the diameter of the drum base should be 30 cm.

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